

CAUSES OF DETERIORATION OF ECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article talks about ecology, the concept of nature, the impact of the aggravation of the ecological situation on the decrease of the population's income, the impact of environmental degradation on human health, today's statistical indicators, ongoing work, plans.

INTRODUCTION

Consistent work is being carried out in our country in the field of environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, improvement of sanitary and ecological conditions.

At the same time, the results of the analysis conducted in this regard indicate the absence of a comprehensive approach and strategic planning in the implementation of state functions in the field of environmental protection, as well as the insufficient powers of the nature protection body to effectively perform the assigned tasks.

Human can never live without nature, because he is an integral part of nature. The universe in which we live and which surrounds us is as kind and lively as our mother. In every particle of the sun, in every body of soil, we feel the loving touch of nature as a mother to us. It embodies thousands of elements necessary for man in every aspect. What is the condition of our beautiful nature today? Who is responsible for this? How can this be prevented? [1-4] are becoming a topical issue today. Unfortunately, humans have an unprecedented impact on nature. It cannot be compared to anything that can be influenced by human intelligence and work. To be more specific, creatures use nature as it is and have an imperceptible effect on it. Humanity can adapt to all the conditions surrounding it, it can not adapt, it adapts it to its own desires, as a result, the balance of nature is disturbed, and the disturbed balance leads to great losses.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The ecological environment surrounding living beings has been changed in a negative way mainly by mankind, the main reason for this is factories, transports and their waste [2-3].

These changes have changed the environment to such an extent that it has affected human health as well as all living things.

Despite the fact that billions of funds have been spent on making great discoveries in

every field of human activity, especially in medicine, in the 21st century, diseases threaten the human body and premature deaths are common in life.

We begin by describing the environmental impacts that cause serious harm to the environment and human health. Here we are not only talking about damage to plants and animals, but these effects also affect people. Usually, the decisions taken are more important to protect human health than to reduce negative impacts on the environment and protect the natural environment.

The main consequences of these effects are the pollution of our planet as a whole. We can see pollution of water, soil, air, destruction of ecosystems, degradation of habitats and more. All these lead to increased disease, loss of biodiversity and health problems in both flora and fauna and humans [5].

It is enough to mention the famous expressions of our great thinker, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, about almost all factors of the environment, which are now called ecology, the influence of humans and creatures on them, and finally, the impact of these factors on humans and creatures. "If there was no dust, a person would live for 1000 years", or: "As long as the air is balanced and clean, it (pneuma) does not contain foreign additives, it is a guarantee of health, otherwise it is prone to various diseases causes" [4-6]. Regarding the environment of the place of residence, it is emphasized in the "Laws of Medicine" and it is said: "The place of residence can affect the body in different ways: high or low place, composition and nature of the soil, abundance or scarcity of water, abundance of trees, cemetery or proximity to mines, etc., are important when choosing a place of residence. These thoughts are about the environment, and we can see that they are relevant in medical ecology.

According to world statistics, 10% of the population dies from old age, 20% from accidents and battles, and 70% from diseases. Also, only 10% of our health depends on medicine, and the remaining 90% depends on ourselves and environmental events.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today, environmental problems pose a serious threat to human health. According to the Global Humanitarian Forum, climate change on our planet kills 300,000 people a year. Three hundred million people live under its negative influence. This is causing serious damage to the economy. Such global problems have a negative impact on the development of the Central Asian region. An example of this is the unpleasant ecological situation along the island, the resulting natural stress, and the problem of desertification. In addition, one of the most dangerous factors of pollution of the earth's surface is radiation. It cannot be seen, heard, tasted or smelled. However, under its influence, the interdependence of systems in the human body is disturbed, and the generatormia, which controls the body with intelligence and understanding, is facing changes that cannot be explained in words. As a result, this small amount of radiation affects certain groups of the population, especially the fetuses of pregnant women, children in the process of growth and development, elderly people with weakened immunity, and people with weak health. Radiation enters our body through various ways (food, water and air) into the blood and bones, damaging the whole human body and causing premature death.

In addition to radiation, harmful emissions from industrial enterprises were nitrates and various toxic killers (pesticides) and mineral fertilizers widely used in agriculture. These harmful substances can enter the human body through food products and cause various

diseases. It is known that the spread of diseases in a region depends on the relationship between the population living in that place and the environment. For example, in places where puddles of water have accumulated, favorable conditions are created for the malaria mosquito to live, and in these places, the possibility of the appearance of malaria disease has arisen. For African sleeping sickness to occur, there must be grasslands. Opisthorchiasis is common in people living near rivers, because the intermediate host of the worm that causes this disease is fish, and the disease is transmitted to humans through fish meat. In addition, we can take as an example allergic diseases that are common among the population [6-7].

Many epidemiological observations show a direct causal relationship between chemical pollution of the environment and the violation of the reproductive function of the population. This was found in working conditions - among workers of metallurgical plants, textile industry, gas and oil processing enterprises, laboratory workers and female surgeons, as well as in settlements with polluted atmosphere, water sources and soil. chemical compounds. In the first and second cases, reproductive function disorders were manifested by an increased risk of termination of pregnancy, spontaneous abortion, complications during pregnancy and childbirth, congenital deformities.

Currently, in our country, the system of stabilizing the sanitary-epidemiological environment, reducing negative effects on nature, and organically organizing ecological and hygienic activities serves to protect human health and ensure stability in terms of infectious diseases. The presence of new environmental conditions causes millions of adaptation processes in the human body, which means that the human body has the ability to recover and adapt to any natural conditions. Our task is to create conditions for the self-adjusting and regenerating biosystem to protect itself from various diseases. In order to strengthen the health of the population and prevent diseases, it is necessary to comply with sanitary and hygiene requirements, and to strengthen medical control in some areas where the ecological situation is extremely difficult.

At present, about 45,000 types of chemical products are produced and sold to the population in various plants and factories, 300 mln. about tons of organic substances are produced and more than a million products are made with their help. However, these chemical substances used in production enter the human body in a certain amount through air, water and food, as a result of which various infectious diseases occur. Because some chemicals are toxic, some are allergenic, carcinogenic (carcinogenic), mutagenic (reproductive) and teratogenic (premature or malformed), fibrogenic (separation of body tissues) has properties. Examples of such chemicals include heavy metals (lead, cadmium, mercury), inorganic gases (sulfur dioxide, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, ozone), silicon dioxide (DDT, chlorinated vinyl, etc.) it can. These chemicals are very dangerous for human health both individually and in a mixture. In recent years, the increase of cancer and the emergence of new types of various diseases are mainly due to the influence of chemistry.

It is not a secret to anyone that during the period of technical development, atmospheric air pollution has increased significantly in Almalik, Chirchik, Fergana and Navoi regions of our Republic. Taking the example of Navoi region alone, it is possible to observe the high level of atmospheric air pollution. There are many industrial enterprises that pollute the air in the city of Navoi, which has about two hundred thousand inhabitants. 637,600 tons of harmful substances are produced annually in the technological processes of production, of which

97.2% are retained. Sludge treatment facilities for nitrogen oxides produced during gas burning at the enterprises of the Navoi thermal power plant are planned, but the level of these substances remains above the norm. The program "Environmental protection of Navoi region for 2016-2022" was developed in order to unify ecological balance in the region. Along with industrial enterprises, the increase of motor vehicles in the city also has a negative impact on the city's air.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to reduce the waste of industrial enterprises, first of all, we should widely use the technology without waste, using the advanced technologies that meet the requirements of the present time. After all, the question of waste is one of the important problems in ecology, and if they are processed or processed according to hygienic requirements, we will not only benefit economically, but also prevent pollution of the earth, air, water, food products, and people's health. will be of great importance in the protection of nature and we will deliver our nature for the next generation while preserving its purity.

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